

FUNCTIONAL AND METHODOLOGICAL SUBSYSTEMS OF CONTENT TRANSFORMATIONS OF OPERATING SYSTEMS FOR ENTERPRISES-STAKEHOLDERS IN THE "SMART HOUSE" PROJECTS

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Abstract

The concept of "Smart House" projects represents the integration of information and information and communication technologies. From a technological and economic-management point of view, the development scenario of "Smart House" projects should be based on four basic components: smart physical infrastructure; smart digital infrastructure, digital platforms, integrated digital platforms. The goal of the project is to increase competitiveness, form an effective management system of the city economy, and create safe and comfortable living conditions for residents. The key attributes of a smart city are the manufacturability of the city infrastructure, high-quality management of city resources, emphasis on economic efficiency, including the service component of the city environment, a comfortable and safe environment, and human orientation. The main tool for implementing this is the wide implementation of advanced digital and engineering solutions in the city infrastructure. From the point of view of technology, the digital transformation of cities is based on several megatrends in the field of ICT technologies, namely: mobility; social communications; cloud technologies; big data and predictive analytics; machine learning and artificial intelligence; technologies for ensuring cyber security; internet of things.

The concept of introducing lifecycle management system construction objects using BIM implementation in directions renovation projects is proposed. The necessity of evolution of information technology IoT from smart things to smart planet is presented. The basic structure of the BIM platform is described, which consists of four components. There are Cloud Computing, Big Data analytics, Internet of Things and Blockchain information technologies. The result of the study is a model of a digital project company for management of the life cycle of a construction object. Such management model of virtual design enterprise will optimize and reduce the costs of the existing management systems. With further development and implementation, this management model on the industry BIM platform can form integration basis for the information technologies for reorganization of business processes of the construction enterprise. The future research prospect is creation of an integrated innovative framework supporting digital transformation in the construction industry.

Keywords: *digital transformation, economic-management point of view, Building Information Modeling, Internet of Things, IoT, Big Data Analytics.*

The term "smart home" was coined and put into use by the American Association of Home Builders in 1984. It was then that the decline in prices for electrical appliances began, which made it possible to build offices with high functionality. At the end of the 20th century, intelligent household appliances and new multimedia control technologies began to appear. Multifunctional "Smart House" systems, which provide comfort and safety of housing, are gaining more and more popularity every year. First, it is related to the increase in technological literacy of ordinary people against the background of the development of the digital industry. Secondly, such equipment is gradually becoming cheaper, which makes it more accessible to the broad masses of the population. Currently, "Smart House" systems are installed on both residential and commercial real estate: apartments, cottages, offices, hotels, SPA centers. In Western Europe, as well as in the USA, Canada and other developed countries, such software and hardware complexes are actively used not only by well-off people, but also by those who, due to their physical characteristics, cannot fully live and lead their lives independently.

Home automation or domotics is building automation for a home, called a smart home or smart house. A home automation system will monitor and/or control home attributes such as lighting, climate, entertainment systems, and appliances. It may also include home security such as access control and alarm systems. When connected with the Internet, home devices are an important constituent of the Internet of Things ("IoT").

A home automation system typically connects controlled devices to a central smart home hub (sometimes called a "gateway"). The user interface for control of the system uses either wall-mounted terminals, tablet or desktop computers, a mobile phone application, or a Web interface that may also be accessible off-site through the Internet.

While there are many competing vendors, there are increasing efforts towards open source systems. However, there are issues with the current state of home automation including a lack of standardized security measures and deprecation of older devices without backwards compatibility.

Home automation has high potential for sharing data between family members or trusted individuals for personal security and could lead to energy saving

measures with a positive environmental impact in the future.

Home automation is prevalent in a variety of different realms, including:

- Heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC): it is possible to have remote control of all home energy monitors over the internet incorporating a simple and friendly user interface.
- Lighting control system: a "smart" network that incorporates communication between various lighting system inputs and outputs, using one or more central computing devices.
- Occupancy-aware control system: it is possible to sense the occupancy of the home using smart meters^[11] and environmental sensors like CO₂ sensors,^[12] which can be integrated into the building automation system to trigger automatic responses for energy efficiency and building comfort applications.
- Appliance control and integration with the smart grid and a smart meter, taking advantage, for instance, of high solar panel output in the middle of the day to run washing machines.
- Home robots and security: a household security system integrated with a home automation system can provide additional services such as remote surveillance of security cameras over the Internet, or access control and central locking of all perimeter doors and windows.^[15]
 - Leak detection, smoke and CO detectors
 - Laundry-folding machine, self-making bed
 - Indoor positioning systems (IPS).
 - Home automation for the elderly and disabled.
 - Pet and baby care, for example tracking the pets and babies' movements and controlling pet access rights.

On the presented logical-semantic scheme in the paradigm of cybernetics of problem-oriented modeling, the main subject-object (object-subject) horizontal connections of the constituent elements are abstractly distinguished, each pair of which is determined by the correspondence of its own level of digital modeling.

At the first (I) level of digital modeling of subject-object relationships (the top line of the names of the verticals of subjects and objects in *Fig. 1*, they are formalized, often in a simple arbitrary or established format, with a description that establishes a direct correspondence between a set of plans and a set of goals. The inverse object-subject connection presupposes the influence of the correction of goals on the plans for their implementation, and the conditionally symmetric subject-object connection (the bottom line of the names of the verticals of objects and subjects in *Fig. 1*) changes the scheme of priority of correspondence to the opposite - a set of goals is associated with a set of plans.

For the conceptual simplicity of the general logic of the scheme, the presented system technology of digital modeling of creative activity establishes a conditionally direct correspondence of the levels of digital modeling to the levels of BIM dimension. So, the first (I) level of digital modeling corresponds to the first (1D) level of BIM dimension. Similarly, in the logic of the system engineering scheme of digital modeling of creative activity, seven levels are distinguished, corresponding to six levels of aggregation of entities in terms of subject-object (object-subject) relationships: "plan-goal", "object-project", "process-time", "technology-economy", "system-resource", "complex-convergence".

Figure 1. System engineering of digital modeling in design activity

At the second (II) and third (III) levels, the project formalizes two and three-dimensional models of some object of creative activity, respectively. A reverse object-subject relationship assumes the influence of a set of design conditions and constraints on the object itself, and a conventionally symmetric subject-object relationship changes the matching priority scheme to the opposite, when an object is created based on a design priority established for any reason (for example, using a typical project). It should be noted that the essence of the relationship “object-project” of the second (II) and third (III) levels of digital modeling is not limited to two and three-dimensional visualization of the object, but is the basis for the automation and optimization of variant design, design and intelligent parameterization of the project.

The second (II) and third (III) digital modeling levels are defined by the second (2D) and third (3D) BIM dimension levels, respectively.

At the fourth (IV) level, the processes that make up creative activity are formalized by the time necessary for them. Inverse object-subject communication assumes the influence of temporary conditions and restrictions on the processes under consideration, and conditionally symmetric subject-object communication changes the scheme of priority of correspondence to the opposite, when a set of processes is formed based on conditions and time constraints (for example, fixed

terms of commissioning of critical for infrastructure object). The essence of the “process” in the scheme is aggregated by their exhaustive formulation of a specific task set (production, organizational, management processes, etc.).

The fourth (IV) level of digital modeling corresponds to the fourth (4D) level of BIM dimension.

At the fifth (V) level, technologies used in creative activity are formalized by an assessment of the cost of their application. Reverse object-subject communication assumes the direct influence of economic conditions and restrictions on the technologies used, and conditionally symmetric subject-object communication changes the scheme of the priority of correspondence to the opposite, when technological schemes are formed based on financial conditions and restrictions (for example, the availability of one or another technological equipment).

The fifth (V) level of digital modeling is defined as the fifth (5D) level of BIM dimension.

At the sixth (VI) level, the considered objects, processes and technologies that make up construction systems are formalized by the aggregation of all types of resource support for creative activity, presented at the previous levels of digital modeling by economics and time. The inverse object-subject connection assumes the influence of resource conditions and restrictions on the systems under consideration, and the conditionally

symmetric subject-object connection changes the scheme of the priority of correspondence to the opposite, when the construction system itself is formed based on the conditions and resource constraints (for example, construction in conditions of interruptions in the supply of construction materials or lack of qualified personnel). The essence of the “system” in the scheme corresponds to the definition of a “building system” as a finite set of functional components (elements, objects, construction complex) and the relationship between them, allocated in accordance with a specific goal within a certain time interval [1]. The essence of “resources” is aggregated by their exhaustive formulation of a specific task set (material, technical, labor, organizational, etc.).

The sixth (VI) level of digital modeling corresponds to the sixth (6D) level of BIM dimension.

At the seventh (VII) level, building systems that make up creative activity are combined into complexes that additionally include qualitatively different systems (for example, social or biosphere [9]) and constitute an object of digital modeling of a new class in terms of convergence. The inverse object-subject connection presupposes the influence of qualitatively different in relation to building systems on the complexes in which they are considered, and the conditionally symmetric subject-object connection changes the scheme of the priority of correspondence to the opposite, when qualitatively different in relation to building systems significantly affect the complexes of building systems regardless of their positioning in relation to the complex under consideration (for example, the influence of the geopolitical situation on the course of dependent construction projects).

It should be especially noted that the analysis and solution of most of the tasks of the new, mentioned above, stage of creative activity (stage 4 in Fig. 1) is formalized in terms of convergence precisely at this level of digital modeling.

The seventh (VII) level of digital modeling is defined by an extended seventh (7 + D) level of BIM dimension, which implies further abstraction of any next level of digital modeling of the qualitative convergence of components of systems of various properties (8D, 9D, ..., ND), objectively limited, however, the actual state of the scientific, technical and social progress of society, on the one hand, the objectivity of necessity and elementary common sense, on the other.

Any scaling of the I-VI levels of digital modeling and the corresponding BIM dimension levels is currently objectively exhausted by the framework of the six presented levels of entity aggregation in terms of

subject-object (object-subject) relationships: “plan-goal”, “object-project”, “process-time”, “technology-economy”, “system-resource”, “complex-convergence”.

All levels of digital models of the presented system engineering of creative activity are connected by object, by object and by the logic of digital models itself arbitrarily. Any designated level of digital modeling of creative activity is open for organizing connections with digital modeling systems external to the complex under consideration (for example, weather forecasting).

The described approach to the construction of subject-object and object-subject direct and feedback links at the model level makes it possible to correctly understand the essence and revise the emphasis in many completely practical areas of innovative development and construction industry regulation.

The concept is based on the relevant information data of the construction project as the basis of the model, establishes a 3D information model of the construction project and simulates the real information that the building receives through digital information modeling [1-3].

BIM technology has many features such as visual analysis, collision checking and construction schedule simulation. With the established BIM model, solar radiation, ventilation and lighting of buildings can be modeled to determine the most appropriate location and spacing of buildings, and to formulate reasonable structural design schemes and scientific approaches that effectively reduce the energy consumption of a building [4-7].

The concept of introducing lifecycle management system construction objects using BIM implementation in directions renovation projects presents in the *Table 1*.

Direction of the concept for the implementation of a lifecycle management system for capital construction objects using information modeling technology, taking into account the proposed additions, which we considered earlier, provides for the introduction of the latest technologies that support business processes, government functions and public services within the framework of building and structure lifecycle management using information modeling. Within the framework of this direction, it is advisable to integrate BIM and IoT as an actively developing area of Internet infrastructure development in the world, providing enhanced connectivity of devices, systems and services and their interaction with each other.

Table 1.

The concept of introducing lifecycle management system construction objects using BIM implementation in directions renovation projects

Directions	Description
First	Formation of the legal framework of implementation of life cycle management of buildings and structures with the use of information modeling
Second	Implementation of the construction information classifier and ensuring its interconnection with existing international and national classifiers
Third	Formation of methodological, regulatory and technical foundations for managing the life cycle of buildings and structures using information modeling
Fourth	Introduction of modern technologies and platform solutions that support business processes, state functions and public services within the lifecycle management of buildings and structures with the use of BIM
Fifth	Formation of legal, technological and organizational foundations for the exchange of data and ensuring their reliability and relevance in information resources that make up the digital ecosystem for managing the life cycle of buildings and structures using BIM
Sixth	Development and implementation of professional training programs for specialists in the field of BIM in construction
Seventh	Development and implementation of performance indicators of the life cycle management system for buildings and structures using information modeling
Eighth	Development and implementation of performance indicators for renovation projects of territories (residential areas), including complexes of buildings and structures using information modeling
Ninth	Strategic planning of the resource base for current and major repairs in order to extend the life cycle of buildings within the predicted time frame using information modeling
Tenth	Development and implementation of indicators of investment attractiveness and efficiency of renovation projects of territories (residential areas) using information modeling for the state and for business in the long term

Integrating BIM with real-time data from IoT devices is a powerful paradigm for applications that improve construction and operational efficiency. Numerous applications enable real-time data streams from the rapidly expanding set of IoTs for high-fidelity BIMs. However, research on the integration of BIM and IoT is still at an early stage, it is necessary to understand the current situation of the integration of BIM and IoT devices [7].

In essence, construction is project management. With digitalization, it turns into control based on data obtained automatically at the point of their origin from IoT devices and sensors, connected machines, platforms and equipment, which allow creating information and mathematical models and algorithms, and realizing more and more autonomous production and business processes having the property of adaptability.

That is, the basis for digitalization of construction is informational and mathematical modeling of end-to-end processes, which allows to optimize work in terms of cost, timing, business sustainability and minimization of negative environmental impact, and any other specified characteristics, based on high quality data (in terms of parameters – relevance, accuracy and completeness).

International experience shows that the digital transformation of the economy puts forward new requirements for finding effective solutions for the functioning and development of cities. All this necessitates the development of a strategy for the development of a modern urban environment based on the elements of a smart city. The latter is an innovative city, in which information and communication technologies (hereinafter referred to as ICT) and technical devices that ensure the collection, processing and reception of information

are used to improve the quality of life, the efficient functioning of city systems and the provision of services, meeting the needs of today and not having a negative impact on the economic, social and ecological components of the city. Modern information technologies of the smart city implement the transition to a data-driven city, which is the result of the digital transformation of the economy and the widespread spread of the Internet. This means that in a smart city there is not only intellectualization, but also digitalization of the urban economy. Currently, a comprehensive scenario of intellectualization and digital transformation for Ukrainian cities has not been formed. All this restrains the development of effective methods of creating smart cities in our country. These structural elements face challenges that affect the processes of digital transformation of the economy. These challenges are: – infrastructural gap and high level of wear and tear of the main infrastructures; - shortage of budgetary resources to solve the current tasks of the functioning of the city and its development; - formation of requirements for all city services and services due to the digitalization of all city structures for the development of new technological solutions; - increase in environmental pollution of the urban environment; - increasing the requirements for the quality of the urban environment and ensuring the safety of the activities of all urban structures and the population. Currently, there are no generally accepted criteria for evaluating the intellectualization of the city. The creation of smart cities depends on many factors, among which the development of the city's information network plays a significant role. Therefore, it is necessary to consider the approaches used in international practice and adapt them for the formation of smart cities in Ukraine.

Kyiv is just starting its way to become a smart city. Currently, the capital has approved the concept "KYIV SMART CITY 2020", which defines the foundations of infrastructural, technological and social development of the city, and also forms a new vector of urban space transformation [5]. This Concept is taken into account when developing city target programs. Among the already implemented technologies, the following can be named: 1) online payment; 2) electronic petition service; 3) intelligent traffic management system. The priority areas of the implementation of the concept are: 1) high-quality communal services, which involves effective management of housing and communal services (energy, water supply/sewerage, waste management, in particular solid household waste processing and wastewater treatment, use and conservation of renewable resources); 2) an innovative environment that should provide special conditions for business and investment attraction, the development of electronic forms of education and the involvement of citizens and businesses in the field of urban innovations; 3) e-governance, on the basis of which Kyiv should become a democratic city, whose residents will be involved in city management; the definition of the capital's development strategy, transparency and control over city policy are foreseen; 4) medicine, which includes the use of technologies to ensure safety, quick response to emergency calls, attention to the problems of Kyiv residents.

In order to secure the information technologies of a smart city from various types of attacks, it is necessary to develop the standards of the "Information technologies for the implementation of the digital transformation of the economy" series. The objects of standardization include technologies: – the Internet of Things, the Internet of Buildings, the Internet of Energy, the Internet of Transport; – information modeling in construction; – cloud technologies and platforms; – big data; – distributed registers, etc.

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